

A Synthesis of *o*-methylkigelin

J. N. CHATTERJEA*, C. BHAKTA and N. D. SINHA

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-5

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A synthesis of *o*-methylkigelin has been carried out by way of the related isochroman (XII). The isochroman was prepared under critically controlled conditions from the propanol (VII).

KIGELIN (I), a dihydroisocoumarin was isolated from the *Kigelia pinnata* by Govindachari *et al.*¹ along with 6-demethylkigelin (II), some sterols and *o*-methylmellein. The structure of kigelin was assigned on the basis of spectroscopic and degradative studies and its synthesis has been reported². We now report our synthesis which was carried out on similar lines.

3,4,5-Trimethoxybenzyl methyl ketone^{3,4} (VI) was conveniently prepared from 3,4,5-trimethoxyphenylacetic acid⁵ (V) by adapting the method of Hauser and Walker⁶. The latter was prepared in quantity from 3,4,5-trimethoxyacetophenone by Willgerodt reaction. On reaction with NaBH₄, (VI) gave the related carbinol (VII) which on condensation with chloromethylether^{7,8} gave the bis-isochroman (VIII) convertible into the bis-dihydroisocoumarin (IX) on chromic acid oxidation. The structure of the compound was supported by the molecular ion (M⁺ m/e 488) and the fragments (Xa), m/e = 237 (100%) and (Xb), m/e = 251 (100%). Further, the compound showed absence of Ar-H in the P.M.R. spectrum.

However, treatment of (VII) with 1 mole of CH₂O/HCl gave the isochroman (XII) oxidisable to *o*-methylkigelin (IV) identical with the 'natural' product. Use of a slight excess of formaldehyde afforded the chloromethyl derivative (XI) which on chromic acid oxidation gave the aldehyde (III). Partial demethylation of (IV) to (±) kigelin (I) has been carried out².

Experimental

All m.p.s are uncorrected. Unless otherwise mentioned the i.r. spectra were determined in Perkin-Elmer Infrared Spectrophotometer, Model 237.

3,4,5-Trimethoxyphenylacetic acid⁵ (V)

A mixture of 3,4,5-trimethoxyacetophenone (12 g), sulphur (3.74 g) and morpholine (7.19 g) was cautiously heated (in hood). The heating had to be moderated in the beginning to prevent frothing due to evolu-

tion of hydrogen sulphide gas. After 1 hr. the mixture was heated vigorously to refluxing which continued for 10-15 hrs. The crude morpholide so obtained was hydrolysed with a mixture of glacial acetic acid (25 ml), sulphuric acid (7 ml) and water (11 ml). The mixture was brought carefully to the boiling point and refluxed for 5 hrs. The solution was decanted from a little tarry material into a large amount of water. The aqueous soln. was then extracted with chloroform (5 × 30 ml) and washed with water. The chloroform solution was then extracted with aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (20%). The sodium hydroxide extract was boiled with charcoal and filtered. The filtrate was cooled and acidified to get the crude acid, which crystallised from chloroform as colourless needles (7 g), m.p. 120°-21° (lit.⁵, 120°).

3-(3',4',5'-Trimethoxyphenyl)-propan-2-one^{3,4} (VI)

Magnesium ethoxide was prepared by heating a mixture of clean magnesium turnings (1.3 g), dry alcohol (1.3 ml) and CCl₄ (0.2 ml). When the reaction started a mixture of alcohol (5 ml.), dry ether (25 ml.) and diethyl malonate (8.8 g) was added carefully with stirring. The mixture was gently refluxed till all the magnesium nearly dissolved and freshly prepared 3,4,5-trimethoxyphenylacetyl chloride (7.5 g) in ether (40 ml) was added with constant shaking and the mixture heated further for 1 hr. when the magnesium complex separated as jelly. The reaction mixture was decomposed with dil. sulphuric acid (2*N*) and the ethereal layer which contained the malonate derivative was separated, solvent removed and the residue hydrolysed with a mixture of acetic acid (30 ml.), sulphuric acid (4 ml) and water (10 ml) under reflux for 5 hr. Acetic acid removed under reduced pressure on water-bath. It was then diluted and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution (10%), then with water and dried (MgSO₄). Removal of the solvent afforded a thick brown liquid distilling at (bath temp.) 150°-160°/2.5 mm. as a colourless oil (4.0 g) which solidified (> C = O 1705 cm⁻¹), m.p. 67°-68° (lit.^{3,4} 66°-67°). Found: C, 64.54; H, 7.78. Calc. for C₁₂H₁₆O₄: C, 64.30; H, 7.14%. The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from ethyl

* Present address: Indian Lac Research Institute, Nankum, Ranchi-10.

acetate, m.p. 165°. Found : N, 13.45. $C_{18}H_{20}O_7N_4$ requires : N, 13.86%.

as a colourless oil, (2.1 g), ν_{max}^{neat} 3450 cm^{-1} (lit.², sublimation at 120°-30°/0.1 mm.). Found : C, 63.57; H, 7.78. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{16}O_4$: C, 63.74; H, 7.96%.

3-(3',4',5'-Trimethoxyphenyl)propanol-2-ol (VII)

A mixture of aqueous sodium borohydride (0.45 g in 15 ml) and sodium hydroxide soln. (1 ml, 10%)

Action of Monochloromethylether on (VII)

To a mixture of ethereal solution of the alcohol (VII) (1.7 g in 30 ml) and monochloromethylether

- I, R = R₂ = H, R₁ = CH₃
- II, R = R₁ = R₂ = H
- III, R = CHO, R₁ = R₂ = CH₃
- IV, R = H, R₁ = R₂ = CH₃

V,

VI, R = O

VII, R = H, OH

VIII, R = H₂

IX, R = O

$Xa, \frac{m}{e} = 237 (100\%)$

$Xb, \frac{m}{e} = 251 (100\%)$

XI, R = CH₂Cl

XII, R = H

was added dropwise to the methanolic solution of the ketone (2.4 g in 15 ml) with constant shaking in 15 min. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature and excess of borohydride was decomposed carefully with conc. sulphuric acid. The aqueous soln. was extracted with ether (4×30 ml). Total ether extracts was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution (10%), satd. sodium bisulphite soln., satd. sodium chloride solution and finally with water. Removal of the solvent afforded thick yellow liquid which distilled at (bath temp.) 180°-90°/2 mm.

(0.7 g in dry ether, 10 ml), freshly prepared zinc chloride powder (1.10 g) was added slowly with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was slightly warmed on water-bath for 5 min, cooled and decomposed with water. The ether layer separated and the aqueous layer was extracted with ether (2×10 ml). The ethereal extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution (10%), with water and dried (MgSO₄). On removal of ether (VIII) was obtained as a solid which crystallised from benzene as pale yellow prisms (1.2 g), m.p. 158°-59°. Found :

C, 65.72; H, 7.3. $C_{27}H_{36}O_8$ requires C, 66.39; H, 6.55%.

Oxidation of bis-isochroman (VIII)

The above compound (VIII) (0.71 g) was dissolved in acetic acid (7.5 ml) and cooled at 0°–5°. A soln. of chromic oxide (0.57 g) in acetic acid (8.4 ml) and water (2.2 ml) was added dropwise with constant shaking during $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The reaction mixture was left at room temp. for 2 hr. and warmed on water-bath at 60° for 15 min. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water and extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water and then dried ($CaCl_2$). A yellow liquid obtained on removal of benzene, crystallised from pet. ether (40°–60°) as yellow needles (0.35 g), m.p. 107°–9°; ν_{max}^{KB} 1730 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl). Found: C, 62.25; H, 6.8. $C_{27}H_{32}O_{10}$ requires C, 62.79; H, 6.2%.

Action of Excess of Formaldehyde (1.5 moles) and Hydrochloric acid on the Alcohol (VII)

To an ethereal solution of the alcohol (VII) (1.13 g in 20 ml) a mixture of formaldehyde soln. (0.63 ml, 40%) and conc. hydrochloric acid (0.62 ml) was added with constant shaking. The mixture was allowed to stand at room temp. for 15 min. and then warmed on water-bath at 40° for 5 min. The reaction mixture was diluted with water, ether layer separated and aqueous layer extracted with ether (2 × 15 ml). On working up (XI) distilled at (bath temp.) 150°–55°/2 mm. as a colourless oil (0.75 g). Found: C, 58.25; H, 6.79. $C_{14}H_{19}O_4Cl$ requires C, 58.63; H, 6.6%.

Oxidation of (XI)

The above compound (0.71 g) was dissolved in acetic acid (7.5 ml) and cooled at 0°–5°. A soln. of chromic oxide in acetic acid (10 ml) and water (3.2 ml) was added dropwise. On working up the product as before, an aldehyde was obtained as colourless needles, m.p. 95°; ν_{max}^{KB} 1690 (-CHO) & 1730 cm^{-1} (lactone carbonyl). This was identified as 5-formyl-3-methyl-6,7,8-trimethoxydihydroisocoumarin (III). Found:

C, 59.5; H, 5.9. $C_{14}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 60.0; H, 5.71%. The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 220°–21°. Found: N, 12.15%. $C_{20}H_{20}O_9N_4$ requires N, 12.17%.

Action of Formaldehyde (1 mole) and Hydrochloric acid on the Carbinol (VII)

The alcohol (2.26 g) in ether (40 ml) was treated with a formalin solution (0.83 ml, 1 mole) and conc. hydrochloric acid (0.83 ml) with constant shaking. The reaction mixture was worked up in usual manner after 5 min, giving (XII) as a liquid b.p. 160°–70°/2 mm. Found: C, 65.2; H, 7.8. $C_{13}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 65.54; H, 7.56%.

Oxidation of the Isochroman (XII)

The compound (XII) (0.69 in 7.5 ml. acetic acid) was treated with a soln. of chromic oxide (0.63 g) in acetic acid (10 ml) and water (3.2 ml). The reaction mixture was worked as before. The resulting oil on chromatography over alumina in benzene afforded (\pm) *o*-methylkigelin, m.p. 101°–2° raised to 105° on crystallisation from *n*-hexane. The compound had identical i.r. spectrum as authentic specimen kindly provided by Prof. T. R. Govindachari. Found: C, 61.65; H, 6.5. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{16}O_5$: C, 61.90; H, 6.31%.

References

1. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, S. J. PATANKAR and N. VISWANATHAN, *Phytochemistry*, 1971, 10, 1603.
2. T. R. GOVINDACHARI, S. J. PATANKAR and N. VISWANATHAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 507.
3. J. M. PEPPER and M. SAHA, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1964, 42, 113.
4. D. F. REINHOLD and M. SLITZINGER, U.S. Pat 3,344,023; *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, 68, 96127.
5. K. H. SLOTTA and J. MILLER, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1936, 16, 238.
6. C. R. HAUSER and H. Q. WALKER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1386.
7. R. QUELET, *Compt. rend.*, 1933, 198, 1411; *Chem. Abs.*, 1933, 27, 3921.
8. R. QUELET, *Compt. rend.*, 1934, 198, 102; *Chem. Abs.*, 1934, 28, 2687.